

AWARENESS ON PROFESSIONAL COURSES AMONG TRIBAL IN NILGIRI DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Education is the core of human development and enrichment of life style. It possesses the power to restructure the social balance, economic status, strengthen customs, break the superstitious beliefs and uplift the human race. It is essential to make aware of such power to every human community. The presents study helps to nurture the importance of Education in general and awareness on professional courses in particular among the tribal parents in Nilgiri district. The study was a normative survey preformed with a self-made Awareness Scale that was standardized by content validity. The reliability coefficient of the tool was calculated as 0.63. The awareness on professional courses is the dependent variable and the independent variables in this study are educational status, economic status, family type, nature of job and graduation status of tribal parents. The tool was administered to 270 tribal parents living in Kodery village in Nilgiri district. The results were tabulated and subjected for inferential statistics. The results show that the awareness on professional courses among tribal parents has to be augmented.

Introduction:

The tribal people are rich in cultural heritage and skill of art and craft but they are still marginalized in respect to higher education as well as in other walks of life. But the tribes, who are the custodians of Indian culture in real sense, are far behind in this race of advancement. Scheduled Tribes in India are generally considered to be Adivasis, meaning indigenous people or original inhabitants of the country. The tribes have been confined to low status and are often physically and socially isolated instead of being absorbed in the mainstream of Hindu population. Since the 16th century, the tribes have been perceived as sub-humans who live under primitive conditions. All the reasons are the root cause of the alienation of tribal in education and the dropout.

According to the Report of the Education Commission (1964-66), the education of the backward classes in general and of the tribes in particular is a major programme of equalisation and national integration. No expenditure is too great for the purpose. (Government of India, 1966). The Government of India and the State Governments have been implementing various special education schemes and programs for the socio-economic development of the tribes. In order to meet the demands of the society, tribal people must be aware of professional courses for selecting their profession. Professional course is a course that leads to a professional qualification. A professional qualification will entitle one to register with a professional body like the Institution of Engineers, Medical Association, Association of Chartered Accountants, teachers, lawyers etc.

The Nilgiri is one of the oldest mountain ranges, located at the tri-junction of Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Karnataka. It has large volume of tribal population. Since there are many critical issues and problems in the field of tribal professional education, the present study emphasizes to know the awareness of these people at least on colleges offering professional education with many scholarships for tribal. Government schools are available separately for tribal students in the Nilgiri. But as far as the professional

education is concerned separate colleges for tribal students are not available in the hilly areas as it is highly not possible. Considering these issues, the investigator has selected this problem for the present investigation.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the present study are,

- ✓ To investigate the awareness on Professional Courses among the tribal in Kodery village.
- ✓ To analyze the difference in the awareness of Professional Courses among people with respect to gender, education status, economic status, family type, nature of job and graduation status of tribal.

Hypothesis:

Based on the objectives, six null hypotheses were formulated for the present study.

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to Gender.
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to their Educational Status.
- H₀₃: There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to their Economic Status.
- H₀₄: There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to their Family Type.
- H₀₅: There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to their Nature of Job.
- H₀₆: There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to Graduation Status.

Delimitations:

The delimitations of the present study are,

- ✓ The sample selected for the study is not a state wide one. The study is confined to Kodery village situated in The Nilgiri district only.
- ✓ The investigation is administered only to Badaga people of Nilgiri district who belongs to the group tribal.
- ✓ The number of tribal people in Nilgiri district is too large; hence the investigator restricted the sample size to 270 living in Kodery village.

Research Methodology:

As the present study deals with fact finding, the investigator adopted Normative Survey Method to measure the Awareness on Profession Courses among Tribal in Kodery village. Variables are the conditions or characteristics that the investigator manipulates, controls or observes. Jaeger (1990) defines independent variables are antecedent conditions that are presumed to affect a dependent variable. The awareness of tribal is the dependent variable used in this study. The independent variables in this study are gender, educational status, economic status, family type, nature of job and graduation status of tribal.

Tool Used:

A self-made Awareness Scale was used by the investigator for the present study. The tool was in the form of a questionnaire. The tool was constructed under five dimensions of awareness. They are awareness about courses in Engineering, Medical, Accountant, Teaching and Law. The scale is in the form of Yes or No type questions. The investigator scored 1 mark for the every correct response and 0 for wrong response. The investigator constructed the tool based on the tribal knowledge on duration of a

course, eligibility for a course, eligibility marks to be obtained for a course and scope of the course. The Awareness scale consists of 30 items.

Tool Standardization:

The investigator employed a pilot study to validate the self-made tool. The pilot study was conducted to 32 tribal in Maniyapura Village near Coonoor. The initial draft of the Awareness Scale consists of 40 statements under five dimensions. Out of 40 statements, 10 statements having t-value less than 1.76 were deleted and the remaining 30 statements were shuffled to form the final draft of the scale. The test-retest method was used to measure the reliability coefficient. The reliability was calculated as 0.63. Since the calculated reliability value is greater than 0.50, the final draft of the Awareness Scale is found to be reliable for the present study. In this study content and face validity was used to observe the validity of the tool.

Sample Selection:

As the present study is a fact finding method, the investigator adopted simple random sampling technique. All the tribal constituted the population of the study. The sample for this study is 270 tribal from Kodery village. The samples were the mixture of tribal belongs to the Thodas, the Kurumbas, the Badagas, the Irulas, the Mullukrumbans, the Paniyas, the Kattunaickens and the Kotas.

Table 1: Distribution of Sample

Gender		Education Status		Economic Status		Family Type		Nature of Job			Graduation Status		
Male	Female	Literate	Illiterate	<10000	>10000	Joint family	Nuclear family	Govt. Job	Private Job	No Job	First Graduate	Graduate	Un Graduate
122	148	68	202	87	183	194	76	68	162	40	110	69	91

Data Gathering Procedure:

The investigator visited the Kodery village and met the tribal head to get necessary permission to conduct the survey. The samples were given all necessary guidance during data collection process. The objectives of the study were explained to tribal and their consent and cooperation were sought in fixing a suitable date and time for filling the tool. After getting necessary permission from the village head, the investigator visited the village at various time based on the availability of samples. The samples were requested to answer all the items in the scale. The investigator assisted the illiterate samples in responding the questionnaire without bias. The filled in questionnaire was collected, scored and preserved by the investigator for further interpretation.

Hypothesis Testing:

Awareness of Tribal on Professional Course with respect to Gender, Educational Status, Economic Status and Family Type:

Table 2: Mean, Standard deviation and t- value: Gender, Educational Status, Economic Status and Family Type

Hypothesis	Variable	Sample	Mean	S.D	't' value
H ₀₁	Male	122	17.23	4.60	2.90*
	Female	148	15.52	5.08	
H ₀₂	Illiterate	68	10.92	0.90	14.03*

	Literate	202	18.31	4.30	
H₀₃	Income below Rs.10,000	87	11.29	1.02	17.05*
	Income above Rs.10,000	183	18.90	4.09	
H₀₄	Joint family	194	18.30	4.58	12.53*
	Nuclear family	76	11.73	1.38	

* Significant at 0.05 level

From the above table it is observed that the calculated t-value for all hypotheses are greater than the table value and so significant at 0.05 level. Hence all the hypotheses are rejected. However the significant difference among male and female in awareness on Professional courses is less than the significant difference of any other hypotheses. The difference level is greater with respect to the economic status of tribal when compared to their gender, educational status and family type.

Awareness of Tribal on Professional Course with respect to their Nature of Job:

Table 3: Mean, Standard deviation: Nature of Job

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Govt	68	20.42	3.61719
Private	162	16.97	4.58725
No Job	40	11.00	0.67937
Total	270	16.13	4.93789

Table 4: ANOVA with respect to Nature of Job

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2276.433	2	1138.217	70.96*	.000
Within Groups	4282.534	267	16.039		
Total	6558.967	269			

* Significant at 0.05 level

From the above table, it is clear that the calculated F value 70.96 is greater than the table value at 5% significance level. Hence the null hypothesis, "There is no significant difference among Tribal in Awareness on Professional Course with respect to their Nature of Job" is rejected. The tribal who are working in government, private management and without job have different level of awareness on professional courses. This result reveals that, awareness of tribal on professional course is affected by their job nature. The mean score of the three groups shows that the tribal who have government job possess high awareness on professional courses when compared to the tribal who are working in private management and are jobless.

Awareness of Tribal on Professional Course with respect to Graduation Status:

Table 5: Mean, Standard deviation: Graduation Status

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
First Graduate	110	16.99	3.18683
Graduate	69	22.37	2.70131
Un Graduate	91	11.31	1.07372
Total	270	16.45	4.93789

Table 6: ANOVA with respect to Graduation Status

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4852.015	2	2426.007	379.47*	.000
Within Groups	1706.952	267	6.393		

Total	6558.967	269			
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**Significant at 0.05 level*

From the above table, it is clear that the calculated F value 379 is greater than the table value at 5% significance level. The null hypothesis, "There is no significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to graduation status" is rejected. Thus there is a significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to graduation status. It is concluded that the first Graduate, graduate and un graduate tribal have different level of awareness on professional courses. Also the mean score reveals that the tribal graduates have greater awareness on professional courses when compared to the other two groups.

Major Findings:

The major findings of the present study based on research data analysis and its interpretation are listed below.

- H₀₁:** The null hypothesis "There is no significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to their educational status" is rejected. Therefore there is a significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to their educational status. Also, the literate tribal have better awareness on professional courses than illiterate tribal in Kodery village.
- H₀₂:** The null hypothesis "There is no significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to their economic status" is rejected. Hence there is a significant difference among the tribal with respect to their income. This result reveals that, the tribal with income more than Rs.10,000 per month have more awareness when compared to the tribal with income less than Rs.10,000 per month.
- H₀₃:** The null hypothesis "There is no significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to their family type" is rejected. It is concluded that people who live in joint family and nuclear family have different level of awareness on professional courses. Also, the awareness is greater for the tribal living in joint family than the tribal living in nuclear family.
- H₀₄:** The null hypothesis "There is no significant difference among Tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to their nature of job" is rejected. The tribal who are working in government, private management and without job have different level of awareness on professional courses. The mean score of the three groups shows that the tribal who have government job possess high awareness on professional courses when compared to the tribal who are working in private management and are jobless.
- H₀₅:** The null hypothesis "There is no significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to graduation status" is rejected. Thus there is a significant difference among tribal in awareness on professional course with respect to graduation status. Also the mean score reveals that the first graduates have greater awareness on professional courses when compared to the other two groups.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of the study, the followings measures were recommended to improve the professional course awareness of tribal in Kodery village in Nilgiri district.

- ✓ A sound awareness has to be created in general and particularly among the tribal whose economic status are low, by ways of rally, NSS camps organized by colleges, etc.
- ✓ Establishment of professional course institution within easy accessibility;
- ✓ Establishment of Guidance and Counselling centers for people to create awareness about professional course.
- ✓ Motivating all the parents to send the children to professional course and not to work, and creating awareness to the Kodery tribal families about the education facilities provided by the Government and employment opportunities.

Conclusion:

In the present study, an attempt was made to examine awareness of tribal on professional courses in the Nilgiri district. In the field of education, teacher plays a vital role in the progress of student life. The tribes are guided by their parents to continue their family job like cattle grazing, labour for tea estates etc. Hence appropriate awareness at right time on education and in selecting professional course for their children helps to uplift the life of tribal. The true knowledge about educational courses and carrier opportunities should be provided with equality. The government has framed many policy measures for the development of tribal. The teachers who are developing the tribal children in lower level shall pass the knowledge of government schemes and various policy measures to those children and their parents for their better socio economic status. The growth of the nation lies within the growth of all community in every part of the country.

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